

Transforming bauxite residue into high performance inorganic polymers: a feasible solution for all european refineries?

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Abstract

The sustainable use of industrial residues allows to lower the environmental impact of the construction industry. Within this framework, use of bauxite residue (BR) is of high interest, because of the large available volumes. Although BR is considered to be highly alkaline for cementitious systems, it can be a suitable precursor for inorganic polymers (IPs) in case the material is transformed into a reactive glass through a heat treatment. This paper shows that BR produced in different European refineries can be converted to different reactive precursors with similar chemistry at temperatures of 1200 °C, considerably lower than conventional cement production. Compressive strength up to 100 MPa, using solely alkali-activated treated BR (TBR) and sand, was achieved under ambient curing conditions. The sodium content in the TBR precursor was identified as one of the key elements in promoting the early and late age performance.

Introduction

The green deal is a new growth strategy for Europe to lower its environmental impact, pushing the industry towards sustainable innovation. This deal will also impact the construction industry requesting a decrease in its environmental footprint by either minimizing the amount of emitted CO₂ during the production of ordinary Portland cement (OPC)¹ and/or by opening the door to alternative, more sustainable binders. Inorganic polymers (IPs), used in mortars and concrete, are a promising alternative to partially replace these binders. Bauxite residue (BR) is of high interest to produce these IPs because of its inherent high alkalinity, which is needed for the production of IPs. However, BR shows a low intrinsic reactivity in alkaline conditions and therefore is preferably mixed with -for instance- ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS) or fly ash²⁻⁴. Several works have focused on increasing the reactivity of BR through a heat treatment⁵⁻⁷. At 1100 °C, BR was transformed with additional C and SiO₂ into a reactive precursor for alkaline activation with compressive strength up to 43 MPa. Further research showed that

by treating BR (>80 wt%) at 1200 - 1300 °C with C, SiO₂ and CaO, compressive strength up to 130 MPa could be achieved⁷. This high compressive strength was used to define an optimal precursor chemistry for treated BR (TBR). In this work, BR from different EU refineries are converged to this optimal chemistry by adding C, SiO₂ and Na₂CO₃. The effect of these adjustments is analyzed by quantitative X-ray diffraction (QXRD), compressive strength and shrinkage measurements.

Methodology

Bauxite residue (BR) was delivered by Aughinish Alumina (IR), Alum Tulcea (RO) and Aluminium of Greece, Mytilineos S.A. (GR). BR_IR and BR_RO were supplied in a slurry state and were first filtered and dried at 105 ± 5 °C for 24 h, while BR_GR was solely dried. The chemical analysis of the residues was performed using a Bruker S8 Tiger Wavelength Dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (WDXRF) following a lithium borate and lithium bromide fusion with 10 wt% BR sample at 1050 °C to form fusion beads. Thermal analyses were performed on the different raw materials using the TA SDT Q600 in order to determine the amount of bound water and carbonates, and to calculate the loss on ignition (LOI) at 1000 °C.

BR samples were converged to the optimal chemistry described in ⁷ and referred in this work as the target chemistry. A fixed amount of C/Fe₂O₃ (0.05) was added in the mix to achieve an equal carbothermic reduction. SiO₂, CaO and Na₂CO₃ were added to dried BR in varying amounts in order to achieve the target chemistry. These are noted as Ca, Si and Na in the naming of the samples e.g. ROSi1010; 10g of SiO₂ and 10 g of CaO added to 100g of BR_RO.

High-temperature melting of the BR was performed in an Indutherm induction furnace. Alumina crucibles containing the mixes, were heated using a surrounding SiC crucible. During the heating, N₂ gas was blown on top of the samples with a rate of 60 l/h. At melting, the gas mixture was changed to CO/CO₂, to ensure the formation of the desirable Fe²⁺. After 2h of equilibration at the target temperature the (partial) melt was quenched in water. Later, the treated BR (TBR) was dried at 105 ± 5 °C for 12h. After drying, the material was homogenized and milled to a grain size <500 µm and characterised in terms of density. The TBR was further milled to a specific surface area of 4500 ± 200 cm²/g according to EN 196-6 using an attritor ball mill.

The mineralogical composition of the TBR was measured with a Bruker D2 Phaser X-ray diffractometer and quantified using the internal standard method and Rietveld analysis⁸. IP mortars were produced by mixing the 0.45 wt% of TBR with a sodium silicate activating solution (SiO₂/Na₂O=2.0, 65% H₂O) and CEN sand (1350 g). This procedure only deviates from the EN 196-1 regarding the amount of binder and liquid over solid, which is recalculated using the of the precursor density. After casting, the samples were cured at 20 ± 2 °C for 24 h, while

being still in the mould. After 24 h the samples were demoulded, wrapped in plastic foil and stored. Samples for drying shrinkage were cured after demoulding without cover at 20 ± 2 °C and 40 ± 10 % humidity and the length change was measured at different time intervals. The compressive and flexural strength for the wrapped samples were tested using an Instron 5985 testing machine with a load rate of 2 and 1 mm/min, respectively.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows a high content in Fe and Al in the studied BR samples. The Si, Ti, Ca and Na concentrations varied between the different residues.

Table 1. Normalised chemical analysis (WDXRF) of the studied BR samples from EU refineries (BR_IR, BR_RO and BR_GR).

(wt%)	BR_IR	BR_RO	BR_GR
Fe₂O₃	50.1	46.0	49.4
Al₂O₃	17.6	22.3	22.6
SiO₂	10.8	14.0	9.0
CaO	5.5	5.0	9.1
TiO₂	9.6	3.6	5.9
Na₂O	6.2	8.8	3.7
MgO	0.2	0.2	0.2
K₂O	<i>bdl</i>	<i>bdl</i>	0.1
MnO	<i>bdl</i>	<i>bdl</i>	<i>bdl</i>
LOI *	9.8	11.7	6.4

* LOI measured using TGA of samples dried at 105 °C.
bdl: below detection limit.

Table 2 shows the major elements concentration of the melted residues with fluxes (TBR). The bulk Si and Ca content was adjusted to similar concentrations for RO-Si10Ca10, IR-Si12Ca8, GR-Si15Ca5 and GR-Si15Ca7Na10 by the addition of the CaO and SiO₂. Only GRSi15Ca7Na10 had additional Na₂O to investigate its effect. Although Table 2 shows that the bulk chemical composition was quite comparable for all the samples, different mineralogy and compressive strength were obtained for the TBR and resulting IP.

Table 2. Normalised chemical analysis (WDXRF) for the melted fluxed residues (TBR).

	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Na ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	Other
Target *	38.1	18.9	19.3	7.4	12.4	2.9	0.9
RO-Si10Ca10	37.4	20.1	19.4	7.8	12.2	2.9	0.2
IR-Si12Ca8	39.6	15.0	20.9	5.4	11.5	7.3	0.3
GR-Si15Ca5	40.0	19.4	21.1	3.1	11.3	4.8	0.3
GR-Si15Ca7Na10	38.0	17.4	20.1	7.5	12.2	4.5	0.4

* Target: It concerns the chemistry of the most reactive precursors identified in ⁷.

The bulk mineralogy of the TBR samples is visualized in Figure 1. The crystalline phases are mainly iron-rich phases (mainly spinel solid solutions), whereas a significant amount of an amorphous compound is present in all the TBR samples. The amorphous phase, which is the reactive component for producing IPs, ranges from 51 to 72 wt%. Some of the added flux was incorporated in the crystalline gehlenite (Ca₂Al(AlSi)O₇). This is undesirable, as the amorphous phase is considered to be the main reactive phase in alkaline solutions⁷.

Figure 1. Quantitative mineralogy of TBR determined using Rietveld analysis (QXRD).

Compressive strength reached up to 100 MPa after 28 d using BR_RO. It is remarkable that, samples using BR_GR with a similar bulk chemical composition as the sample with BR_RO had a considerably lower strength. When sodium was added (GR_Si15Ca8Na10), the 7 d-compressive strength was twofold increased. Furthermore, shrinkage was also affected by an increased concentration of sodium and is half of the GR-Si15Ca5 sample (Figure 2B). The compressive strength was

lower than the 130 MPa reported in⁷ and was most likely affected by the temperature treatment towards TBR due to precipitation of gehlenite, decreasing the amount of CaO in the amorphous phase and final binder. Ca plays an important role in the strength development and shrinkage^{7,10}. A second reason is the use of a higher L/S in the sample preparation.

Figure 2. A) Compressive strength of mortars using the different TBR. B) Shrinkage under 35% humidity up to 28 days.

The linear relationship between the compressive strength and the amount of Na₂O of the TBR also implies their positive correlation (Figure 3). It is noteworthy to mention that no Na-bearing crystalline phase was detected by QXRD study and Na₂O is therefore most likely only present in the reactive amorphous phase of the studied samples. The Na₂O decreases the polymerization of the glass, improving dissolution kinetics¹¹. Furthermore, Na can accelerate glass dissolution by dissociation of water in OH⁻, resulting in faster formation of the binder. Because the Na₂O is shown to be quite important in obtaining high performance binders, it implies that the treatment of the residue after the Bayer process is crucial. If BR is washed intensively, considerable amounts of sodium needed to be added as flux to the treatment or in the later activating solution to increase performance. Otherwise, BR has to be fluxed with higher amounts of CaCO₃ and SiO₂ to obtain high performance binders using solely TBR.

Figure 3. The linear relationship between the Na₂O content and the compressive strength shows their positive correlation.

Conclusion

This study shows the successful transformation of BR into high performance IP binders. By adding C, SiO₂, CaO and Na₂CO₃ the residue was transformed at temperatures of 1200 °C to a semi-vitrified glass with an amorphous phase content between 51 and 72 wt%. By alkaline activation of the residue, compressive strengths up to 100 MPa were obtained. No Na-bearing crystalline phases were detected by QXRD; thus Na was likely fully incorporated in the amorphous phase. A positive correlation between the Na₂O content in the TBRs and compressive strengths were observed. This implies that if high performance is targeted, treatment after the Bayer process is crucial.

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References

1. European Commission, "The European Green Deal," https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en, 2020
2. N. Ye, J. Yang, X. Ke, J. Zhu, Y. Li, C. Xiang, H. Wang, L. Li, & B. Xiao, "Synthesis and characterization of geopolymer from bayer red mud with thermal pretreatment," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **97**, no. 5, pp. 1652-1660, 2014.

3. X. Ke, S. A. Bernal, N. Ye, J. L. Provis, and J. Yang, "One-part geopolymers based on thermally treated red Mud/NaOH blends," *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **98**, no. 1, pp. 5-11, 2015.
4. N. Ye, J. Yang, S. Liang, Y. Hu, J. Hu, B. Xiao, & Q. Huang, "Synthesis and strength optimization of one-part geopolymer based on red mud," *Constr. Build. Mater.*, **111**, pp. 317-325, 2016.
5. T. Hertel, B. Blanpain, and Y. Pontikes, "A Proposal for a 100 % Use of Bauxite Residue Towards Inorganic Polymer Mortar," *J. Sustain. Metall.*, **2**, no. 4, pp. 394-404, 2016.
6. T. Hertel, A. Van den Bulck, B. Blanpain, and Y. Pontikes, "Correlating the amorphous phase structure of vitrified bauxite residue (red mud) to the initial reactivity in binder systems," *Submitt. a*, 2020.
7. M. Giels, T. Hertel, and Y. Pontikes, "Producing ambient cured high performance Inorganic Polymer mortars using solely vitrified bauxite residue. Engineering and understanding the effect of process parameters on the resulting binders," *In preparation*, 2020.
8. R. Snellings, L. Machiels, G. Mertens, and J. Elsen, "Rietveld Refinement strategy for Quantitative Phase analysis of Partially Amorphous zeolitized tuffaceous rocks," *Geol. Belgica*, **13**, pp. 183-196, 2010.
9. M. Giels, T. Hertel, and Y. Pontikes, "Transformation of bauxite residue into highly reactive precursors for Inorganic Polymers, feasible in industry?," *In preparation*, 2020.
10. G. Ascensão, G. Beersaerts, M. Marchi, M. Segata, F. Faleschini, and Y. Pontikes, "Shrinkage and Mitigation Strategies to Improve the Dimensional Stability of CaO-FeOx-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ Inorganic Polymers," *Mater*, **12**, no. 22, pp. 3679-3699, 2019.
11. B. Mysen and P. Richet, *Silicate Glasses and Melts*, 2005.